

Commemoration and Historical Memory of World War II in Nigeria

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Abstract

The central focus of this paper is the commemoration and historical memory of World War II in Nigeria. While history is replete with instances where people all over the world have come to share in a somber healing ritual of honouring their nation's soldiers killed in battle, recently, emphasis has shifted to public commemorations as a way of remembering those citizens who fought and died for their nation. Especially after World War II, many nations built ceremonial graves, monuments, museums, memorials etc, to honour their soldiers killed in the great conflict. This paper examined the critical role of memory in representing the past (WWII) and argues that memory has become one of the central driving force, framework and methodology that questions the past and how it is remembered both individually and collectively. The paper adopts the qualitative approach, utilizing primary and secondary sources to interrogate issues of commemoration and historical memory as well as associated dynamics. The paper submits that, memory is not just a function of the past, but also adds value and meaning to commemoration of events in the present. In addition, it is the argument in this paper that historical memory allows individuals and societies to remember (or forget) certain moments or events in their history as a function of the reconstruction of their present. As a result, public presentation of memories is not only a useful method of engaging the past, but also has the potential force to transform the collective memory of the nation.

Keywords: *History, Oral history, Commemoration, Remembrance, Memory and Historical memory.*

INTRODUCTION

By the end of the First World War, which heralded the defeat of Germany and its allies, people expected lasting peace in the world. At least the establishment of the League of Nations after the war was a clear attempt at forestalling future wars. Unfortunately, the dynamics of the interplay of forces propelled the world into an even more destructive and deadlier catastrophic war twenty-one years later. After 1918, Germany had only waited for an early opportunity to revoke the Treaty of Versailles which was excruciatingly humiliating her sovereignty. Germany had surrendered on the peace terms of the Allied Forces that were considerably unfavourable. There was, however, the threat that the war would resume if Germany did not sign the treaty, which completely undermined her national pride. Under such shameful conditions, the German delegates had forcibly signed the Treaty of

Versailles. The Germans openly registered their embittered disposition to the government for signing this disgraceful treaty.

The deplorable post-war conditions in Europe definitely germinated and fertilized in Germans who looked forward to survivors who would solve their teething problems. And this vacuum was ostensibly provided by Adolf Hitler. He had in many occasions vehemently argued that the Treaty of Versailles was a quagmire of sort with little relevance either in thought or in writing. The dreams to get his country back on track struck in 1921, when he became head of the Nazi party, with the primary aim of overturning the treaty of Versailles. Concocting the seemingly spectacular rise of Germany Rao writes that “it was an irony of fate that Germany, a nation mortified after the Great War, arose as it were from the ashes to strike at her erstwhile tormentors within a short span of 20 years”.¹ By whichever measure, the resurgence of Germany was remarkable and for twenty years (1919-1939) another world war was inevitable, especially as Hitler repeatedly declared openly that “those who want to live, let them fight, and those who do not want to fight in this world of eternal struggle do not deserve to live”.² Europe therefore became a veritable theater for the emergence of dictators; extreme nationalism; the violation of the Treaty of Versailles; the alliance systems; failure of the League of Nations to keep peace and ensure disarmament; and more fundamental, Germany’s invasion of Poland on September 1 1939, snowballed the whole of Europe back into the battlefield.

Over the years after World War II almost every nation that participated or experienced the war had its own way of dealing with the past. Some nations, like Germany, could not deny the immense guilt and responsibility that weighed heavily on the German citizens. Germany would spend decades dealing with its past and seeking reconciliation with their victims. Germany’s World War II history was indeed, an “unmasterable past”.³ For many other nations, however, the social lines between being guilt and being a victim were characterized by mixed feelings. Nigeria for example, held on for generations to the myths surrounding their involvement in this seemingly Europeans’ war.

The concern of this paper is not to establish what exactly the Nigerians did or did not do during World War II. Rather, the paper is focused on how the war has been remembered in Nigeria. The engagement of memory studies in this context is not about whether Nigerians’ behaviour during the war was complicit but rather to comprehend the dialectic between remembering and forgetting certain historical events, and the process of constructing a national or collective memory. It is vital to assimilate the difference between actual historical facts and how nations remember them, acknowledging the historical truth irrevocably connecting memory and facts. In contemporary traditions, past events happened the way they have been remembered and told in the national historical narrative.

As a result, this paper is essentially to describe and analyze how the axial of commemoration and historical memory of World War II was constructed, maintained and modified in the decades following it. Furthermore, it seeks to establish the role of Nigerians during the war and how they were remembered after 1945, shaping their collective memory of the war, and the consequences the different ways of remembering ultimately had on them. For the most part, collective memory was shaped due to political exigency dictating these historical constructions. Arguably, contemporary politics at any given time situates how these myths through historians, public officials, and the media plays to the gallery of World War II as well as how the long tradition of Nigerian history shapes these myths. It was this official re-interpretation of Nigerian governments' historical narrative of its World War II involvement and interaction with the outside world that Nigerians have been stifled in various ways, in the context of this discourse.

HISTORICAL MEMORY: A CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Academic exercise as a continuous parade of idea unfolding through time, appears as a sequence of intellectual fashions which leads to the evolution of axial concepts around which an entire body of ideas oscillates. This cyclic order of ideas can be called the "Mnemonic turn" which defines the concept of "memory" as an engine room for intellectual debates of the moment. Collective memory, a term whose conceptual paternity belongs to the French philosopher and sociologist Maurice Halbachs, has gained a strong currency in the market place of idea exchanged in the social sciences and humanities. In his book on collective memory he defines the concept as a flexible, constantly changing and socially constructed idea. Once thought to be the refuge of the individual, it is influenced by the collective or social memory as individuals are relying on society to remember. He wrote thus:

Yet it is in society that people normally acquire their memories. It is also in society that they recall, recognize, and localize their memories {...} it is in this sense that there exists a collective memory and social framework for memory; it is to the degree that our individual thought places itself in these frameworks and participates in this memory that it is capable of the act of recollection.⁴

Accordingly every group, he argued, develops a memory that highlights its own past and its unique identity. The social frameworks of collective memory, mediate individual memories, and there is a strong "presentist" dimension in that social groups determine what is memorable and how it will be remembered.⁵ Collective memory is both what individuals jointly remember from their own life experience and what is collectively commemorated without being personally experienced. Stated differently, collective memory consists of the common stock of personal memories of public events plus the package of "second hand" memories that are historically inherited and shared by a pool of individuals forming a social community.⁶

It is also adjudged as impermanent and changing as society evolves. As an example Halbwachs, shares how the constructed image and memory that the mediaeval pilgrims had of Jerusalem was entirely different from the image other pilgrims cultivated at another time in history. Despite these differences collective memory is not at cross-fire, but greatly influenced by the social situation and spatial condition upon which the memory is constructed. For Halbwachs:

The past is a social construction mainly, if not wholly, shaped by the concerns of the present. He argues that the beliefs, interests, and aspirations of the present shape the various views of the past as they are manifested respectively in every historical epoch.⁷

How the memory of the past is directly influenced by the actions of the present is amply demonstrated in the way or manner Nigerians remembered the World War II. The memory of this great war is one of 'presentist' as the memorials, museums, and public commemorations etc. tend to agree with Halbwachs concept of collective memory because they tell the same story about their heroic deeds, at different times and under different circumstances, to 'remember' a completely different historical aspect of the War. Corroboratively therefore, a study on the Nigerians' memory of World War II in the present is as much a study of its historical events. Nigeria, for example, tends to remember or commemorates their falling heroes in grand styles mimicking the civil war heroes on the 15th January of every year, but then shares the story of veterans of the World War II.

Halbwachs idea on collective memory provoked the writings of Pierre Nora, a French historian, in his seventeen volume work 'Realms of Memory' (1981-1992), where he articulated a wide range of 'memory sites' that are germane for the national identity of his country France. In conceptualizing the idea of collective memory and history he argues that:

Memory is life, borne by living societies founded in its names. It remains in permanent evolution, open to the dialectic of remembering and forgetting, unconscious of its successive deformations, vulnerable to manipulation and appropriation, susceptible to being long dormant and periodically revived. History, on the other hand, is the reconstruction, always problematic and incomplete, of what is no longer. Memory is a perpetually actual phenomenon, a bond tying us to the eternal present; history is a representation of the past.⁸

In his conceptualization of collective memory Nora agrees with Halbwachs' idea that memory is shaped by the activities of the present. He further spotlights the difference between history and memory. While history attempts to rationally reconstruct what transpired in the past, memory is an organic process that, according to Nora, happens in the present by way of the so-called *liex de mémoire*. The "places of remembrance"

can be found in such places as museums, monuments memorials etc. Nora also warns that memory sites can be interpreted and even manipulated, for nationalistic ends.

Collective memory also radiates or encompasses studies of rituals. In *How Societies Remember* (1989), social anthropologist Paul Connerton examines how ritual performances-for example, the Nazi festivals which were undertaken during the hey-days of the Third Reich- are commemorations that reinforce collective or national identity. For Connerton such ceremonies are performative and are expressed in bodily gestures. As witnessed in commemorative stance across the globe as match-passes and parades undertaken by veterans demonstrate solidarity rituals as a common exercise among veterans and the general public is well acquainted.⁹

Similarly, political anthropologist John Gillis throws more light on memory construction and commemoration in consonance with the idea of social and national identity. He writes quite aptly that:

We need to be reminded that memories and identities are not fixed things, but representations or reconstructions of reality, subjective rather than objective phenomena. We are constantly revising our memories to suite our current identities. Memories help us make sense of the world we live in; and ‘memory work’ is embedded in complex class, gender and power relations that determine what is remembered (or forgotten), by whom, and for what end national identities are, like everything, constructed and reconstructed.¹⁰

While reflecting on the different types of memory, Jan Assmann, a German historian of ancient Egypt expanded the notion of memory developed by Maurice Halbwachs. He advances the important distinction between what he calls communicative memory and cultural memory, which according to him differ in the first place in their distance into time to the actual event. For Assmann, communicative memory only serves a limited time frame for contemporary witnesses to a particular event. He argues forcefully that:

Its most important characteristics is in its limited temporal horizon. As all oral history studies suggest, this horizon does not extend more than eighty to (at the very most) one hundred years into the past, which equal three or four generations...¹¹

From a different perspective, communicative memory actually focuses on the shared memories of a social community that are based solely upon everyday communication, being derived from personal experiences and preserved in the form of oral tradition (i.e. “first hand” social memory). While cultural memory consists of the representations of the past transposed into a cultural support (usually written texts, but also material artifacts such as statues, monuments, memorials etc) that enhances the

inter-generational transmission of social memories (i.e. “second hand” collective memory).¹² Therefore, following the template of Jan Assmann’s time span of up to one hundred years we find a different type of memory, which is culturally rooted. Cultural memory in this context is not only unique in its distance to the event and the fact that it does not change with time, but also in its function. Assmann is a constructionist and in his view cultural memory does not deal with the “real other”, but with human constructions and projections of the other. This is a clear variant of Halbwachs’ views on history and memory, however, Assmann is only keen about the critical importance of cultural memory.

In an attempt to regularize the thoughts of Halbwachs theory of “collective memory” Jeffrey Olick defines it more broadly by systematizing the uniqueness of individual memory. He writes that:

Collective memory is merely a broad, sensitizing umbrella, and not a precise operational definition. For, upon closer examination, collective memory really refers to a wide variety of mnemonic products and practices, often quite different from one another. The former (products) includes stories, rituals, books, presentations, speeches, images...etc; the latter (practices include reminiscence, recall, representation, commemoration. To focus on collective memory as a variety of products and practices is, thus, to reframe the antagonism between individualist and collectivist approaches to memory more productively as a matter of moments in a dynamic process. This, to me, is the real message of Halbwachs’ diverse insights.¹³

COMMEMORATION

Commemoration has become increasingly commonplace, deeply ingrained in the cultural lives of nations. Not only have nations come to embrace traditional forms of commemoration, but they have pioneered new practices and methodologies, especially in the remembrance of people who died as a result of war. The first key question might be what is commemoration? The dictionary defines commemoration as the “call to remembrance; to mark an event or person or a group by a ceremony or an observance or a monument of sort. Commemoration takes varied dimensions but the common motif is that it constitutes collective or social memory in some conspicuous way.

Fittingly, the custom of paying homage or respect in public to ordinary soldiers killed in debacles dates back from the beginning of ideas of nations and citizenship during the second half of the nineteenth century. The First World War was the initial conflict known to have evoked the situation where dead people are consistently buried and commemorated on memorials as individuals, systematizing the commemorative ideas or traditions that are still in vogue.¹⁴

The practice of commemoration of war dead, according to King serves dual purposes: “affirmation and propagation of political idea about wars and the nations which fight them” and “the need to express and resolve emotional traumas caused by war”. Both dimensions are seemingly like a web as the former is generally associated with the state, whereas the latter concerns the domain of individual mourners and veteran as much as to groups.¹⁵

In Nigeria, as elsewhere around the globe, the twentieth century marked the watershed for war, death in war, and commemoration has been tied to the image and power of the state. In pursuit of their foreign policy objectives several nations engaged in many conflicts compelling citizens to serve in the armed forces. For example, the colonial West African states under their masters (especially Britain, France and Germany) served in the colonial armed forces, fought in many war fronts in Europe, Asia and Africa. It is in this stance that the state or nation shapes its relationship with the war dead through commemoration. The consequence of which is to present the dead as “the courageous, the heroes who made the supreme sacrifice. Accordingly, there is nothing to raise questions about the appropriateness of this sacrifice, or its necessity, or the conditions under which it occurred”.¹⁶

Put differently, to systematize the power of state a national myth is constructed to justify the actions which emphasize the meaningfulness of fighting and individual sacrifices to the state. This is essentially to make an unpalatable past acceptable, above all for the justification of the nation in whose name the war had been fought. State needs commemoration to provide an acceptable explanation for death in war, so that it can call its citizens to risk their lives whenever the need arises.

Going forward, war deaths, therefore, is a representation of the inability of states to protect its citizens. In an attempt to do this the state therefore internalizes the occurrence of their deaths: “the crime committed by enemies as an act of humiliating violence to the nation is symbolically inverted and claimed to be instead an expiatory sacrifice made on behalf of the nation for its own survival and renewal”.¹⁷ Perhaps, surprisingly, the nation is said to have sacrificed its most resourceful citizens on the altar of war, for survival and regeneration as well. Consequent on the said sacrifice made on behalf of the nation the dead entered the realm of morally cleansed icons, heroes or guidance of the nation or martyrs as the case may be. What then are the medium through which Nigerians commemorate or remember the World War II dead veterans?

The contention here is that the politics exacerbated by the state to have created a measure of divergence in remembering these war deaths, has also been seen to have profoundly shaped the foundation of Nigerians and by extension Africans’ commemorations till date as the table below shows

COMMEMORATIVE TRADITIONS AMONG NIGERIANS

(Table A Tangible)

1.	National War Museums
2.	Memorials
3.	Monuments
4.	Status
5.	Cemetaries
6.	Cenotaphs
7.	Memorial Gardens
8.	Epitaths
9.	Memorabilias
10.	Condolence Registers
11.	Death Rituals (festivals)
12.	Second Burials or rites of passage
13.	Tree Planting
14.	Gravestones
15.	Veteran Associations
16.	Drawing of tattoo of names on the body of relations
17.	Architectural/Building
18.	Parks
19.	National Archives
20.	Public Holidays/Anniversaries
21.	History Books (their roles in history of the war)/Poems
22.	Tablets
23.	Busts
24.	

(Table B Intangible)

1.	Songs
2.	Folktales

3.	Lyrics
4.	Praise drum names (for heroic death)
5.	Proverbial names
6.	Remembrance Anniversaries
7.	Healing of the dead (inofoi) ¹⁸
8.	Duefengu ¹⁹ etc

From the tables above, we have seen the many different dimensions of honouring war deaths following the World War II in Nigeria. The establishment of memorials such as museums, monuments, statues, gravestones among other representations underscores the need to provide a historical basis to project actors of relevance especially as it relates to wars and how this reflects the pursuit of peace and tolerance in the present time. The above examples especially museums tries to achieve this through showing the impact of war on the lives of individual soldiers and civilians. The message is essentially the need to continue to work for peace.

The US Holocaust Memorial Museum for example, suggests that the Holocaust serves as a justification for America and their participation in the World War II. According to Vivian Patraka, “the conferring of liberation (to concentration camp internees) becomes the story of American democracy.

To assert this story entails elevating the masses of people who died before liberation...that saving Jews, Gypies, Leftists, Catholic Dissenters, Homosexuals, and Polish forced labour from the Nazis was one of the goals of World War II, rather than a by-product of winning the war by invading the enemies territories”.²⁰ This simply means that World War II can be remembered as a just or a moral war, which has been severally called “The Good War”. This is no surprise when young viewed the so-called war to be “one of the few remaining anchoring points of (American) national mythology”.²¹ It is a critical reflection that appraises America’s conduct of the World War II as just and moral, re-echoing its global leadership role.

Drawing from the above example, justifies the aphorism that all nations are “imagined communities”. This idea shapes Jemibewon thought when he states war is “a constitutive element of collective identity, reproduced in collective memory through national ‘narrative’ of past glories in the face of threats against national sovereignty and survival”. This is to corroborate the fact that established national war museums that practically plays a part in the creation of a sense of nationhood, and hence commemorates war in an African sense peculiar to them.²²

For instance, Nigeria’s constructed national narratives are myths, in the sense that they are not the real events that occurred but are a reflection of crafted or dramatized story that has evolved in the society to contain the meanings of the war. It is the understanding that this was orchestrated to create tolerance, and to provide meaning to the disarticulations and contradictions associated with the war. Myths about war are

constructed from a variety of sources, including wartime propaganda and later to project veterans and social groups associated with the war.²³ The common practice is that commemorative traditions or customs add to the myth making, utilizing traits such as bravery and patriotism which is attributed to the war dead, and by extension, to other veterans.

Perhaps unsurprisingly, as it is within the ambit of state for the commemoration of war deaths, this tendency seemed to have deprived individual soldiers of their individuality. This is apparently typified by war cemeteries, in which uniform gravestones are placed in regimented fashions (i.e. in Nigeria it's painted green-white-green colours). This seeming loss of individuality is an aspect of a whole by which the state takes control of the memory of war death with national flag and twenty-one gun salute. Giving credence to this ritualistic aspect of state commemoration of war death, Rowlands adduces that "nationalist war memorial...turn traumatic individual deaths into acts of national celebration and assertions of collective value".²⁴

Going by other commemorative practices, there are three typically important ways that individual war dead can be remembered or commemorated by the state: as martyrs sacrifice for the nation, as victims, as heroes. In military cycle, there is a traditional focus on two types of individual soldiers: those who have won awards for bravery, and those who reached high rank. Such celebrations formed shrines of heroism to the elite of the nation or military unit (either in military museums or post-humorously). "Heroes" definitely play a crucial part in national memory, each being "a cluster of national meaning, in the sense that meaning is imputed to particular persons in order to serve as figures of national bravery, sacrifice and unity".²⁵ Heroes represent the best personalities whose patriotism is demonstrated in war, and to the nation at large.

Similarly, the war dead can graduate into traditional commemorative terms, as martyrs who paid the supreme sacrifice for the nation. This acknowledges loss, but implies that the dead did not die in vain, and that something has nevertheless been gained; and so for Rowlands, a "sense of collective loss" is transformed into "an object of devotion and passion".²⁶ Meanwhile, a third portrayal is as victims. Generally speaking, the three categories are mutually exclusive, although the first two categories can form different part of the web (same narrative). The rituals or memorials of each category are very crucial in the national myths making as the heroes and martyrs monuments as well as statues memorializes feats accomplished while alive. Interestingly, in most cases, the victims' pictorials are preserved in national archives and other repositories (i.e. history books) empathizes their deaths associated with the nation indicating mass burials in military cemeteries.

This apparently in most cases, deposited in galleries, museums, memorials etc dedicated to winners of the highest military decoration. There are cases of display of

each individual hero, with a caption encapsulating the heroic deeds by which the individual achieve this feat of valour (medal), sometime with medals or the display of other relics. Arguably after the First World War, military cemeteries and associated war memorials became what George Mosses called “the sacred spaces of a new civic religion”.²⁷ Corroboratively Jemibewon was quite right when he contends that, “medal galleries are in the same tradition of civic shrines, whether to the regiment and its traditions in the case of regimental museums”.²⁸

In this sense, commemoration of war deaths permits the voices to be heard especially of those who have paid the supreme sacrifice for the nation. This is so because the generation of the World War II veterans is fast disappearing, therefore a museum or memorial must take their place to keep their memories (i.e the national war museum in Nigeria among others established for this purpose). The implication is that without these shrines of commemorative representations giving voice to previously forgotten heroes or individual who have been denied the opportunity to make public their experiences of World War II. Although, this could be seen as counter memorial in the way that it restores their individuality and humanity. But the approach could condense to various devices to ensure that individual deaths are not subsumed within a national narrative, but also to extend the ways or patterns of remembering war deaths in the immediate society. It is also an attempt to preserve memories which will otherwise be lost. This will in no small measure, reflects the special status given in the commemorative tradition to war dead, and by extrapolation to veterans and Holocaust survivors.²⁹

Put differently, memorializing war dead sometimes imply that contemporary societies have an obligation to learn about their past, just as the commemorative tradition has an obligation to share the experiences of the past. This is so, because, the generation of eyewitnesses has gone. It has therefore fallen to contemporary generation to pass on their testimony of what war is all about. Not only does “time heal” but it also leads to fading “twilight memories” as generations die. This is perhaps why Michael Rowlands is of the opinion that:

Ensuring the dead will not be forgotten is one function of memorials, yet forgetting is part of the process of healing and renegotiating memories. The purpose of a memorial is as much as to resolve trauma memories as to preserve them. For both individuals and for societies affected by death in war, commemoration needs to achieve a degree of closure and resolution of suffering as part of the mourning process, through the creation of an appropriate memory.³⁰

Interestingly, commemorative exhibitions are representative attempts both to come to terms with the past and to recall a past which is in danger of extinction (being forgotten). It is also possibly even an attempt by contemporary generations to claim

the past (from survivors and eyewitnesses) as their own, such that memorials and commemorative exhibits, may reflect fading memories or a desire to forget, since building memorials may reduce or diminish one's perceived obligation to remember. Consequently, building memorials may therefore not resolve the challenges or remembrance, particularly if it trivializes those memories or reduces them to clichés. A good example of such is the Vietnam veterans' memorial in Washington (USA), which brewed controversy because it did not use traditional heroic imageries. In the case of World War II, which for many Nigerians was still blurred with an unresolved myth, therefore, this kind of memorials are widely recommended to keep the war memories alive.

HISTORICAL MEMORY AS A BRIDGE

Historical memory like oral history can be an important framework and methodology that repositions questions about the past or lived experiences and how it is remembered, both individually and collectively. Historical memory is significant because, the meaning people make from commemorative events is just as important as what actually happened. The fact is that, society is but interested in the significance of how and what people remember, even when memory is at obverse of the same event. What seems to matter most is how events and their consequences have been able to affect the individual and social community. This is condensed to mean, even if individual or collective memory do not appear real in the form of historical facts and characters, they present accounts that picture a historical period and context, and inscribe a memory of the past in the construct or narrative. The idea behind this is that memory gives history a flow and an emotional meaning and knowledge that one cannot get from elsewhere.³¹

From a different point of view, when destructive or painful historical events happen, there is the tendency of a before, and an after narrative, such that the past of the World War II could certainly help people think about those lived experiences and how to look at the after, or how to manage the post war (the after) social reality. This 'after' of the event entails divergent elements, especially reconstruction from entirely material point of view, but also psychological and emotional. In Nigeria for example, remembering the two historical acts of catastrophe such as colonialism and World War II can, therefore, have a great consequence on the individual and social consciousness, from trauma to shame to anger and so forth. Historical events as the above might be considered a painful experience by those who are being colonized. The call to memory or remembering a period of colonization allows societies to better appreciate the present and contemplate the future. On the other hand, most Nigerians and by extensions Africans were teased to fight the World War II without commensurate recognition or compensation before demobilization by the colonial powers. This made the "Good War" a "hopeless war".³²

As the previous sections have acutely demonstrated, the commemoration of war death heavily relied on historical memory in order to communicate ideas about the past to

the contemporary generation for utilization. But how can historical memory be used as a bridge and line of communication between the two different areas and directions of historical representations. The nexus is that historical memory serves as a key framework and methodology that aid commemoration of events. In order to establish the potential connections between them through the means of historical memory, it is useful to engage the various or different types of commemorative approaches. For example, as aptly demonstrated in the tables discussed previously, the tendency is that, it shapes why the accurate and detail presentation of history depends on collection of what the commemorative motif tells about the events commemorated as in the case of a war museum, monument, memorials etc that can be effectively mediated by historical memory.

It can also be seen as a bridge between the separate historical representations. This is so as it can be employed to construct and understand stories connected to great historical past, similar to the manner or methodology of oral history; despite its limited scope and coverage. Historical memory however, focuses on the construction of the memory rather than the memory itself, the implication is that findings associated with this methodology should not be confused with the factual historical evidence surrounding the event that has been remembered by the social community. It also allows for the consideration of other social histories and constructions, which enables important questions associated with myths making to be raised within the context of a national narrative or history.

Besides being a framework and methodology, historical memory can be seen as a central component of interpretation or in a broader sense, labeled as “performance”. Brittney Boss suggests that, stories, memories and histories are on this account literally ‘performed’ at a number of National Historic Sites that have live interpretation. The recognition accorded the performative aspect of the interpretation allows for a connection to be drawn between commemoration and historical memory like oral history as we have established above. In other words, historical memory maintains focus on the teller of the stories, not the stories themselves. Basically the construction of individual experiences shared is a crucial component of the collective memory generated.³³ It is through this crucial nexus that historical memory allows for the performances of both memory and commemoration to play an effective and central role within the interpretation of any National Historic Site (such as museums, memorials, archives etc)

The ‘Historic Places’ have also recognized the importance of memories and have integrated them into their documentation and performative methods. Museums and its associated platforms such as monuments or memorials encourages individuals to contribute to the space of offering their experiences (stories and memories), which are then integrated into exhibitions. The deposited memories contribute to both the documentation process and the performance of the site. The memories both (written and oral) become a part of the museum space, both tangibly and intangibly, and

contribute to the reconstruction of the collective and individual memories of the nation and its citizens within the context of historical memory, which allows for divergent views about events. Through the inclusion and performance of 'other' voices and memories, the 'Historical Places' can transpose the individual memory of the foreigners and eventually alter the collective memory of the nation as well. It is therefore important to stress that performances are based on socially constructed myths or ideas arising from historical memory.

It also important to stress that commemoration has been diagnosed as a performance, while memory can be said to be a performance wedded with social end result. It can, therefore, be said that it is through this chain or web shared language of 'performance' ideas and historical realities can be infused within collective memory performed at commemoration of historical events through commemorative traditions of social memory. Therefore, the practice of historical memory could engender increased visibility within national narratives and official histories of the nation as well as consistently portrayed as a physical manifestation of national identity. These tangible representations transform otherwise intangible ideas and equally transform themselves into new forms of agencies depicting what Brittney Bos called legitimization that is not found in the realm of the abstract, which according to her significantly impacts the histories of marginalized voices.³⁴ This include individual memories with the focus of engendering connections between the past and present, linking their live experiences, it is in the light of the above that Paul Connerton recognizes that, not only is our view of the present shaped by the image of the past, but our current social order is maintained by the memory and traditions of the past social orders.³⁵ In this new clime there will be a renewed vision and paradigm shift through the effective and progressive connection of historical memory as a bridge or agent of commemorative traditions.

CONCLUSION

This paper has been able to put forward the understanding of commemoration and historical memory which is constructed depending on the social, cultural and political nature as well as the needs and lived experiences, of the society and individuals generating them. It is historical memory that creates commemorative traditions through multiple dimensions such as museums no less than it does to other groups or individuals. While interpreting war and wartime history, Winter suggests that, museums therefore are customized to adhere strictly to traditional customs of commemoration, which according to him, have develop progressively in the twentieth century.³⁶

The idea and practice of memory gave birth to what we called commemorative traditions. The implication is that all aspects of memory commemoration is basically contested, or at best is subjective in nature. It recognizes that, memorials have often been constructed in an attempt to bring together the varied meanings that is associated with death in war has for those left alive, or at least to provide a template for

commemoration which can be given different interpretations or meanings by those producing them. Interestingly, memorials are intended as much to consolidate and draw together (i.e. construct) current shared memories of the social community, especially to create a common past possibly to remember those commemorated.

Following the lessons learnt after the World War I, especially commemoration of war, organized nationally through Armistice Day, predicated to validate the war, and veterans were generally sidelined. In that light World War II veterans have consistently played dominant influence over how the memory of war is represented in public places.³⁷ The decades or so to come will see further changes in commemoration, as veterans might phase out. Their place will be taken by what was referred to as new generations of today's "post-military" society who have very different attitudes to war.³⁸ In the main, therefore, this paper contends that the new attitudinal currency may increasingly develop anti-memorials rather than memorials to war, may lead to a policy of deconstruction of the representation of war. Drawing from the above analysis historical memory which is the engine for progressive framework and methodological approach for both the individual and collective memory will change or persist depending on perception. In sum, the paper therefore argued vehemently that commemoration tradition will persist through people who will seek memorial forms including war museums among others, which can act as "surrogate experiences" so that they can remember a world they never knew or locate themselves in a continuous past. Since nothing lasts forever, memory of war is therefore likely to be more rather than less contested in the future.

ENDNOTES

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